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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of some 5-Arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4- thiadiazoles

S. K. SANGAL* and ASHOK KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

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1,3,4-Thiadiazoles are reported to exhibit broad spectrum of biological properties¹. Thiol group is an important toxophoric group especially active against fungi². The presence of SH group in the thiadiazole nucleus imparts fungitoxicity to these compounds³. A literature survey on 5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-thiols (1) led to the fact that the polynitroarylthio derivatives of this heterocyclic moiety have not been explored for their fungitoxicity. It is well-known that polynitroaryl sulphides possess stronger antifungal properties than the parent mercapto compounds. On the basis of these observations, it was thought of interest to prepare a large number of polynitroarylthio derivatives of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

having halogen, nitro, methyl, methoxy, ethoxy groups at different positions in the 5-phenylamino nucleus with a view to test their antifungal properties and to establish a structure-activity relationship.

5-Arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) have been prepared by the condensation between halogenonitrobenzenes and 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1) in ethanolic solution in the presence of NaOH.

1; R¹ = aryl, R² = H

2; R¹ = aryl, R² = 2,4-dinitrophenyl, 2,4,6-trinitrophenyl, 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl

Thus, three halogenonitrobenzenes have been condensed with nine 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles to give the corresponding 5-arylamino-2-polynitrophenylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (Table 1). The ir spectra of these 5-substituted-arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles agree with their structures. 5-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-5-thiol showed the characteristic ir bands at 3 300 (NH), 2 600 (SH), 715 (C-S), 1 600 (C=N) and 815, 735 cm⁻¹ (substituted-phenyl). These bands are common in these compounds. The band due to thiol disappeared, in addition, in the polynitrophenylthio derivatives strong absorption peaks due

TABLE 1—5-ARYLAMINO-2-POLYNITROARYLTHIO-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE (2)*

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ² **	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% inhibition (1 : 10000)		
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. exigua</i>
1.	Phenyl	(a)	255	95	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	65.0	75.0	55.5
2.	Benzyl	(a)	175	98	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	77.1	81.7	60.4
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(a)	215	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	61.7	66.6	48.2
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(a)	200	97	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	59.8	65.2	47.8
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(a)	199	85	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ ClS ₂	50.9	57.9	53.5
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(a)	177	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	57.7	60.6	54.8
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(a)	191	89	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	59.2	61.1	55.4
8.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(a)	185	75	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₂ S ₂	61.7	60.8	62.7
9.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(a)	140	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	51.8	47.5	55.4
10.	Phenyl	(b)	239	81	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	67.1	78.2	56.1
11.	Benzyl	(b)	168	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	79.3	89.3	62.9
12.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(b)	220	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	63.0	68.1	55.3
13.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(b)	184	94	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂	62.4	67.1	49.3
14.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(b)	210	92	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	53.1	59.6	53.8
15.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(b)	180	83	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂	58.1	62.5	55.7
16.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(b)	215	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	60.0	64.2	57.6
17.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(b)	191	75	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	63.8	58.4	64.9
18.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(b)	155	89	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	47.3	44.6	51.3
19.	Phenyl	(c)	154	77	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	61.1	70.8	54.7
20.	Benzyl	(c)	177	81	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	71.9	76.4	59.1
21.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(c)	188	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	51.7	63.2	48.3
22.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(c)	197	93	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	58.3	64.1	46.7
23.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(c)	165	86	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ O ₆ Cl ₂ S ₂	45.5	55.5	51.3
24.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(c)	171	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	56.6	61.4	54.9
25.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(c)	185	89	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	58.7	63.2	55.9
26.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(c)	215	79	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₆ Cl ₂ S ₂	61.7	56.8	61.7
27.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(c)	195	88	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₈ ClS ₂	46.8	42.9	50.7

* Satisfactory N and S analyses obtained for all the compounds.

** (a) = 2,4-Dinitrophenyl, (b) = 2,4,6-trinitrophenyl, (c) = 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl.

to NO₂ groups⁴ appeared at 1 570–1 580 and 1 400 cm⁻¹, when the thiadiazoles were substituted.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer.

5-Arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles⁵ (1): A mixture of 4-arylthiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol), CS₂ (0.01 mol) and DMF (15 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~1.5 h. The excess of solvent was then removed by distillation. On cooling and keeping the solution for sometime, the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish the desired compound (68%).

Polynitroarylthio derivative of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2): To 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.005 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol by warming, was added a warm solution of 10% NaOH (2 ml) and then refluxed for ~30 min. The resulting light green solution was filtered. To the filtrate was slowly added a solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.5 mol) in alcohol and the mixture shaken, when yellow coloured compounds separated instantaneously. The flask was then kept in warm water to ensure the completion of the reaction and kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol.

Results and Discussion

The 2-polynitroarylthio derivatives of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles are insoluble in water, but dissolve in acetone, chloroform and hot acetic acid. Their melting point and yields are recorded in Table 1.

The thiadiazole derivatives were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Phoma exigua* using Czapek Dox nutrient medium. All the tested compounds possessed significant antifungal activities at 1:10000 concentration. The most active compound of the series was sl. no. 11 (Table 1) which inhibited the growth of all the three fungi significantly; it inhibited the growth of *Aspergillus niger* to the extent of 89.3%. In general, the presence of chlorine atom in R² at C₅ decreased fungitoxicity. Replacement of 4-OCH₃ group by 4-OC₂H₅ has been found to increase fungitoxicity. The increase in the number of nitro groups in R² at *ortho* has been observed to increase fungitoxicity. The following is the decreasing order of fungicidal activity of thiadiazole derivatives with different R¹: benzyl > phenyl > *p*-phenetyl > *p*-anisyl > *m*-chlorophenyl > 5-chloro-*o*-tolyl > 5-nitro-*o*-tolyl.

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Interaction of Alkyl Bromides with 2,4-Dithiobiurets. Formation of Thiuret Derivatives

MADHUKAR S. CHANDE*

and

(Mrs.) NANDITA P. SHETGIRI

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science,
15 Madam Cama Road, Bombay-400 032

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It has been our experience that the alkyl groups which are saturated (such as methyl, ethyl etc.) when loaded on sulphur of the thiocarbamide, are difficult to be dislodged by breaking the S-alkyl bond. There are methods in which Raney nickel is used but it is not advisable to use it in thioureido systems¹. Thioureido compounds containing S alkyl groups can be dealkylated by using hydrogen sulphide, ammonical hydrogen sulphide or H₂S in alkaline medium^{2,3}. Verma⁴ described a method in which thiocarbamide in presence of concentrated HCl debenzylated the S-benzylisothiocarbamides.

In continuation to our work on dithiobiurets^{5,6}, we report here an interesting result observed in the reaction of 1-alkyl- or aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (1) with alkyl bromides, where alkyl group is ethyl or propyl.

On refluxing molar quantities of ethyl bromide and 1-methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (1, R=methyl) in ethanol for 1.5 h, 4-S-ethyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret (2) hydrobromide was obtained in near quantitative yields. The presence of mercaptoethyl group in 2 was evident by its reaction with alkali when ethyl-mercaptan was evolved. On continuing the reflux in ethanol for 5–6 h and working out the reaction mixture, a compound having molecular formula C₈H₈N₂S₂·HBr, m.p. 226°; ν_{max} 1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N),